

Data management plan (DMP)

Nutrition Survey in Montenegro

NutriMont

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	01/12/2023	First draft version of DMP
2.0	08/12/2023	Second version of DMP – Comments and edits on the draft version
3.0	13/12/2023	Final version for submission

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FWF Data Management Plan (DMP)

Guidance and Template

These guidelines are intended to be used as a guidance in the creation of a data management plan for an approved FWF project. This document is based, with minor changes, on the [RDM Guidance for Researchers](#) of Science Europe.

Please answer all the questions in the second column and address the items in the third column. The DMP template can be found at the end of these guidelines, and further information is available in the [DMP Evaluation Rubric](#).

Guidance

I General Information		
I.1 Administrative information	Provide information such as name of principal investigator, FWF project number, and version of DMP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide the relevant grant information. - Consider regular updates of the DMP.
I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources	<p>Who (for example, role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?</p> <p>What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicate who is responsible for implementing the DMP, and for ensuring it is reviewed and, if necessary, revised. - For collaborative projects, explain the co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners. - Explain how the necessary resources (for example, time) to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in. Carefully consider and justify any resources needed to deliver the data. These may include storage costs, hardware, staff time, and repository charges.
II Data Characteristics		
II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data	<p>How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?</p> <p>What data (types, formats, and volumes) will be collected or produced?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain which methodologies or software will be used if new data are collected or produced. - State any constraints on re-use of existing data if there are any. - Explain how data provenance will be documented. - Give details on the kind of data: for example, numeric (databases), textual (documents), image, audio, or video. - Give details on the data format: the way in which the data is encoded for storage, often reflected by the filename extension (for example, pdf, xls, doc, txt, or rdf).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Justify the use of certain formats. For example, decisions may be based on a preference for open formats, standards accepted by data repositories, widespread usage within the research community, or on the software or equipment that will be used. - Give preference to open and standard formats as they facilitate sharing and long-term re-use of data (several repositories provide lists of such 'preferred formats'). - Give details on the volumes (they can be expressed in storage space required (bytes), and/or in numbers of objects/files).
III Documentation and Data Quality		
III.1 Metadata and documentation	What metadata and documentation (for example, the methodology of data collection and way of organising the data) will accompany the data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data. - Use community metadata standards where these are in place (see Digital Curation Center or RDA Metadata Directory). - Consistent, well-ordered research data will be easier to find, understand, and re-use. Indicate how the data will be organised during the project, mentioning for example conventions, version control, and folder structures. - Consider what other documentation is needed to enable re-use. This may include information on the methodology used to collect the data, analytical and procedural information, definitions of variables, units of measurement, and so on. - Consider how this information will be captured and where it will be recorded for example in a database with links to each item, a 'readme' text file, or lab notebooks.
III.2 Data quality control	What data quality control measures will be used?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain how the consistency and quality of data collection will be controlled and documented. This may include processes such as calibration, repeated samples or measurements, standardised data capture, data entry validation, peer review of data, or representation with controlled vocabularies.
IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation		
IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process	<p>How will the data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research process?</p> <p>How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe where the data and metadata will be stored and backed up during research activities and how often the backup will be performed. It is recommended to store data in least at two separate locations. - Give preference to the use of robust, managed storage with automatic backup, such as provided by IT support services of your home institution. Storing data on laptops, stand-alone hard drives, or external storage devices such as USB sticks is not recommended. - Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of a technical incident. - Explain who will have access to the data during the research and how access to data is controlled, especially in collaborative projects. - Explain which institutional data protection policies are in place.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consider data protection (e.g., default technical security measures of the home institution), particularly if your data is sensitive (for example, containing personal data or politically sensitive information). Describe the main risks and how these will be managed during the project.
IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation	<p>How and when will the data be shared? Are there restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?</p> <p>In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use? What persistent identifier (e.g., DOI) and which usage licence (e.g., CC BY) will be used?</p> <p>What methods and software tools are needed to access and use the data?</p> <p>How will data for preservation be selected, and where will the data be preserved long-term?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain how and when the data will be shared. Consider the FWF's Open Access policy on research data. Immediate open access to research data is mandatory for data underpinning research papers, unless there are legal, ethical, or other reasons not to do so. Explain such reasons where applicable. - Explain how the data will be discoverable and made available for re-use, addressing the choice of repository, the persistent identifier (e.g., DOI), and the licence to use (see "How to License Research Data"). When choosing a repository, follow the Science Europe Criteria for the selection of trustworthy repositories and use http://www.re3data.org/ to search for repositories. - Indicate who will be able to use the data. If it is necessary to restrict access or to apply a data sharing agreement, explain how and why. Explain what actions will be taken to overcome or to minimise restrictions. - Describe whether potential users need specific tools to access, interpret, and (re)-use the data (e.g., codes, algorithms). Consider the sustainability of software needed for accessing the data. - Indicate what data must be retained or destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes. - Outline how it will be decided what data to keep and what data not to keep. Describe the data to be preserved long-term and give information on how long and where the data will be retained.
V Legal and Ethical Aspects		
V.1 Legal aspects	<p>How will legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?</p> <p>If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain who will be the owner of the data, meaning who will have the rights to control access. - Make sure to cover the matters of rights to control access to data for multi-partner projects and multiple data owners, in the consortium agreement. - Indicate whether intellectual property rights (for example, Database Directive) are affected. If so, explain which and how will they be dealt with. - Indicate whether there are any restrictions on the re-use of third-party data. - Ensure that when dealing with personal data, data protection laws (for example, GDPR) are complied with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gain informed consent for preservation and/or sharing of personal data. ▪ Consider anonymisation, pseudonymisation, or encryption of personal data for preservation and/or sharing (truly anonymous data are no longer considered personal data). ▪ Explain whether there is a managed access procedure in place for authorised users of personal data.
V.2 Ethical aspects	<p>What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consider whether ethical issues can affect how data are stored and shared, who can see or use them, and how long they are kept. Demonstrate awareness of these aspects and respective planning.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Follow the national and international codes of conducts and institutional ethical guidelines, and check if ethical review (for example, by an ethics committee) is required for data collection in the research project.- Consider "Ethics for researchers" published by the European Commission or "The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity".
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Template

I General Information	
I.1 Administrative information	<p>PI: Andrea Milacic, andrea.milacic@udg.edu.me, ORCID: 0000-0003-1534-1118</p> <p>FWF grant information: OC/EFSA/DATA/2016/03</p> <p>DMP version: 3.0. 13/12/2023</p>
I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources	<p>Person responsible for data management and DMP: Andrea Milacic, andrea.milacic@udg.edu.me, ORCID: 0000-0003-1534-1118</p> <p>Co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners:</p> <p>Data Coordinator</p> <p>Role: This position oversees the overall data management strategy, ensuring compliance with the Data Management Plan (DMP) and coordinating responsibilities across various partners.</p> <p>Position: A dedicated data management professional within the leading institution.</p> <p>Institution: University of Donja Gorica (UDG).</p> <p>Project Researcher</p> <p>Role: All researchers involved in the project.</p> <p>Responsibilities: Provide data which is self-collected, generated, or reused from other sources. Describe the provided data using metadata and deliver it to the corresponding Data Coordinator. Access and use data within the project, respecting any specific access restrictions.</p> <p>Institution: All consortium member institutions.</p> <p>External Researchers/3rd Party Users</p> <p>Role: Individuals outside the project consortium.</p> <p>Access: Allowed to access, utilize, provide feedback on, and cite data that has been marked as public.</p> <p>Restrictions: Subject to data access policies, especially for sensitive or restricted data.</p> <p>Resources costed in for RDM: For the NutriMont project, dedicating adequate resources to data management and ensuring adherence to the FAIR principles is a priority. Financially, this involves allocating funds for data management personnel, whose responsibilities will encompass data curation, storage management, and maintaining FAIR compliance.</p>

In terms of time, significant staff hours will be allocated to various data management activities. This includes time for training staff in FAIR principles and data management best practices, as well as the ongoing tasks of data curation, metadata creation, and ensuring data security and accessibility. Regular audits and updates to data management practices will also be scheduled, ensuring that the project remains aligned with evolving FAIR standards and technological advancements.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Data Management Costs	Personnel	This includes costs for data curation, storage management, metadata creation, and general data maintenance tasks.	2 persons (25% of the engagement)	9.000,00 EUR
Training for Staff	Training	Costs associated with training project staff in data management practices and FAIR principles, possibly including external training courses or materials.	2 training sessions	1.000,00 EUR
Estimated total costs				10.000,00 EUR

Additional description (if required): The data will be stored on TU Wien Research Data - an institutional repository of TU Wien. There will be no costs for depositing public shareable data as the chosen repositories do not apply fees for data storage. Furthermore, collaboration with IT services of TU Wien will be factored in. This collaboration ensures that the data storage solutions are robust and in line with institutional support services, while also providing for backup and recovery processes.

II Data Characteristics

II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

In the NutriMont project, new data will be systematically collected through primary surveys and complemented by secondary data extracted from established datasets. The primary data will include detailed information on dietary habits, health status, and socioeconomic factors, gathered using a General Questionnaire, double 24-hour recall/food forms, and a Food Propensity Questionnaire (FPQ). The data will be processed and analyzed to identify dietary patterns and their associations with health outcomes. The collected data will be organized into several datasets: 1_NutriMont_DemoSocioData, encompassing demographic and sociodemographic survey data in .xls/.xlsx and .csv formats; 2_NutriMont_MacronutrientData, containing detailed macronutrient intake information in similar formats; 3_NutriMont_ConsumptionData, focusing on average food consumption by different food categories; and 4_NutriMont_DataVisuals, comprising data visualizations in jpeg, and .png, formats. External databases are instrumental in filling gaps where our primary data collection might have missing elements. This is particularly vital in ensuring the completeness and accuracy of our dataset, especially in areas critical to our research objectives. Additionally, these databases are extensively utilized for research purposes, particularly in analyzing and drawing meaningful conclusions related to health outcomes.

All datasets will be made available for sharing, re-use, and preservation in structured, non-proprietary formats, adhering to a 3-star level in the 5-star model for open data.

Based on the above explained grouping, the data can be divided into:

1. Databases (structured collections of records stored in a computer system),
2. Digital Objects (e.g. charts, diagrams, images).

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
1_NutriMont_DemoSocioData	Demographic and Sociodemographic Survey Data	Database	.xls/.xlsx .csv (for sharing, re-use ad preservation)	150 KB	No
2_NutriMont_MacronutrientData	Macronutrient Intake	Database	.xls/.xlsx .csv (for sharing, re-use ad preservation)	100 KB	No
3_NutriMont_ConsumptionData	Average food consumption by different food categories	Database	.xls/.xlsx .csv (for sharing, re-use ad preservation)	500 KB	No
4_NutriMont_DataVisuals	Data Visualizations	Image, Graphics, Diagrams	jpeg, .png	5 MB	No

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
NutriMont_FAO_DB	WHO, Nutrition Landscape Information System (NLiS), NLiS Country Profile: Montenegro	https://www.who.int/data/nutrition/nlis/country-profile	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO	No

NutriMont_EFSA_DB	The EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database	European Food Safety Authority, 'The EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database', version 2, 2016 (updated 2018-06-15), accessed 2023-08-08, http://data.europa.eu/88u/dataset/the-efsa-comprehensive-european-food-consumption-database	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence	No
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Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The project utilizes a combination of methodologies and software tools for data generation, processing, and reuse.

Data Collection Methods:

Face-to-Face Interviews - Conducted to gather primary data using a structured questionnaire. These interviews are supplemented with written consent forms to ensure ethical compliance.

Use of Existing Datasets - Data is sourced from repositories, ensuring a comprehensive approach to data collection.

Data Generation and Processing Software:

Diet Asses and Plan (DAP) Platform - This tool plays a pivotal role in standardizing the collection of food consumption data and dietary intake examination. It encompasses:

- Computerized food consumption and physical activity questionnaires.
- Anthropometric measurements recording.
- Integration of the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy.
- A validated food picture book for accurate data collection.
- Data Entry and Processing - All survey data are entered into the DAP platform, which facilitates the initial processing and evaluation of the collected data.

Data Download and Further Analysis:

Data Export Formats: The data of interest are downloaded from the DAP platform in Excel (XLS) and Extensible Markup Language (XML) formats, which are conducive to further analysis.

Analysis Tools: For the statistical analysis and processing of the downloaded data, software tools like Microsoft Excel, and potentially other statistical analysis software like R or Python (with libraries such as pandas for data manipulation), can be employed. These tools allow for detailed data examination, including trend identification, pattern analysis, and correlation studies.

Data Visualization and Reporting:

Visualization Tools: Microsoft Excel will be used for creating data visualizations like charts and graphs, enhancing the comprehensibility of the findings.

Reporting Tools: For compiling reports and research papers, word processing and presentation software like Microsoft Word and PowerPoint will be utilized.

III Documentation and Data Quality

III.1 Metadata and documentation

Data organisation, metadata, and documentation:

Files will be named in a consistent and understandable way. All documents and datasets will be provided with a unique filename to ensure effective version control and data storage. Naming conventions are proposed in the following table.

Dataset ID	File Name
1_NutriMont_DemoSocioData	NutriMont_DemoSocioData_[Date].[FileExtension]
2_NutriMont_MacronutrientData	NutriMont_MacronutrientData_[Date].[FileExtension]
3_NutriMont_ConumptionData	NutriMont_ConsumptionData_[Date].[FileExtension]
4_NutriMont_DataVisuals	NutriMont_Visual_[Topic]_[Date].[FileExtension]

A version control system will be implemented using a platform like GitHub (TUgitLab) for digital documents, and datasets.

Folders will be structured by data type: Raw Data, Processed Data, Analysis, and Documentation. Inside folders (e.g. Raw Data), subfolders will be created (e.g. Surveys Data, and External Datasets).

Metadata

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, a README file at dataset level with an explanation of all values and terms used next to each file with data will be provided.

Each dataset used in the NutriMont project will be followed by data description (general metadata) template. The metadata will be stored in a metadata.txt in each folder of a separate dataset. Additionally, common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories will be provided.

Dataset Metadata Template: A documentation table that is used to describe the metadata of each distinct dataset. The table will be included as a separate metadata.txt file next to each dataset.

Metadata Field	Description (Example Entry)
Dataset ID	Unique identifier for the dataset (e.g., NutriMont_MacronutrientData)
Dataset Title	Concise title of the dataset (e.g., Average food consumption by different food categories)
Date of Collection	Date when data was collected (e.g., 2023-11-15)

	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Data Collector</td> <td>Name/Identifier of individual or team collecting the data (e.g., NutriMont Research Team)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data Source</td> <td>Source of the data (e.g., In-person interviews)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data Format</td> <td>Format of the dataset (e.g., PDF, CSV, PNG)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dataset Description</td> <td>Brief description of what the dataset contains (e.g., Responses from face-to-face interviews conducted in Montenegro)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Keywords</td> <td>Relevant keywords (e.g., nutrition, Montenegro, survey)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Geographic Location</td> <td>Location where data was collected (e.g., Podgorica, Montenegro)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Temporal Coverage</td> <td>Time period covered by the data (e.g., January 2023 - March 2023)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data Format and Structure</td> <td>Description of data organization (e.g., Tabular data, each row represents a response)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Access Conditions</td> <td>Information on data access (e.g., Open access, restricted to project team)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Related Documents</td> <td>Links or references to related documents (e.g., Methodology.md)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Contact Information</td> <td>Contact details for queries about the dataset (E-Mail)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data Citation</td> <td>Preferred citation for the dataset (e.g., NutriMont Project, 2023, Face-to-Face Interview Dataset)</td> </tr> </table>	Data Collector	Name/Identifier of individual or team collecting the data (e.g., NutriMont Research Team)	Data Source	Source of the data (e.g., In-person interviews)	Data Format	Format of the dataset (e.g., PDF, CSV, PNG)	Dataset Description	Brief description of what the dataset contains (e.g., Responses from face-to-face interviews conducted in Montenegro)	Keywords	Relevant keywords (e.g., nutrition, Montenegro, survey)	Geographic Location	Location where data was collected (e.g., Podgorica, Montenegro)	Temporal Coverage	Time period covered by the data (e.g., January 2023 - March 2023)	Data Format and Structure	Description of data organization (e.g., Tabular data, each row represents a response)	Access Conditions	Information on data access (e.g., Open access, restricted to project team)	Related Documents	Links or references to related documents (e.g., Methodology.md)	Contact Information	Contact details for queries about the dataset (E-Mail)	Data Citation	Preferred citation for the dataset (e.g., NutriMont Project, 2023, Face-to-Face Interview Dataset)	
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<p>III.2 Data quality control</p>	<p>Long-term, the datasets will follow the default template provided by the repository (TU Wien Research Data (Test Instance) repository), such as Data Cite Metadata, to ensure metadata interoperability for indexing and discoverability.</p> <p>A far as possible, controlled vocabularies for data will be used to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.</p> <p>Data quality control will be ensured on the following levels:</p> <p>Data Coordinator's Role:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Data Coordinator oversees the integrity and accuracy of the data entered into the system. This includes checking all newly inserted data and food items. • They are responsible for conducting regular reviews and audits of the data, especially after the data collection phase and before the final submission of the dataset. <p>Data Collection Phase Control:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement a rigorous process for data entry, including standard protocols and guidelines that all data collectors must follow. • Utilize standardized data capture methods to ensure uniformity in the information being recorded. <p>Use of DAP Platform for Direct Control:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform control checks directly on the DAP platform. This includes reviewing data entries for adherence to predetermined standards and formats. • The DAP platform's built-in validation tools can be utilized for immediate error detection and correction. 																									

Implementation of Version Control System:
 Utilize a platform like GitHub for version control of all digital documents and datasets. This system will track changes, updates, and revisions made to the data and documents, allowing for the restoration of previous versions if needed and providing a clear history of modifications.

IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation

IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process

Storage and backup facilities:
 Throughout the NutriMont, data and metadata storage and backup will be meticulously managed to ensure data integrity and security. The Data Coordinator, in close collaboration with the designated representative from TU.it, will oversee these processes, utilizing the robust infrastructure of TU Wien.

Storage and Backup

Data Storage: All data and metadata will be stored on secure servers provided by TU Wien. This infrastructure offers robust, managed storage solutions with state-of-the-art security features.

Backup Procedures: Automatic backups will be performed regularly, ensuring that data is copied and stored in at least two separate locations within TU Wien's network. This minimizes the risk of data loss due to hardware failure or other unforeseen incidents.

Backup Frequency: Backups will be scheduled to occur on a weekly basis, with additional backups triggered by significant data updates or changes.

Data Recovery and Access Control

Recovery Plan: In the event of a technical incident, a well-defined data recovery plan will be activated. This plan details the steps to restore data from the latest backups, ensuring minimal disruption to the project.

Access Management: Access to the data will be strictly controlled and limited to authorized project personnel only.

Data security and protection of sensitive data:

The research adheres to TU Wien's institutional data protection policies, ensuring that all data handling practices meet legal and ethical standards. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
1_NutriMont_DemoSocioSurvey	Yes	Yes	Yes

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IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation	<p>Data publication and access conditions:</p> <p>As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in TU Wien Research Data. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>dataset ID</th> <th>access conditions</th> <th>restrictions / embargo reasons</th> <th>estimated publication date</th> <th>location for publication (repository)</th> <th>PID</th> <th>license</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1_NutriMont_DemoSocioSurvey</td> <td>Public</td> <td>N/A</td> <td>December, 2023</td> <td>TU Wien Research Data (Test Instance) repository</td> <td>DOI</td> <td>CC BY 4.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2_NutriMont_MacronutrientData</td> <td>Public</td> <td>N/A</td> <td>December, 2023</td> <td>TU Wien Research Data (Test Instance) repository</td> <td>DOI</td> <td>CC BY 4.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3_NutriMont_ConsumptionData</td> <td>Public</td> <td>N/A</td> <td>December, 2023</td> <td>TU Wien Research Data (Test Instance) repository</td> <td>DOI</td> <td>CC BY 4.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license	1_NutriMont_DemoSocioSurvey	Public	N/A	December, 2023	TU Wien Research Data (Test Instance) repository	DOI	CC BY 4.0	2_NutriMont_MacronutrientData	Public	N/A	December, 2023	TU Wien Research Data (Test Instance) repository	DOI	CC BY 4.0	3_NutriMont_ConsumptionData	Public	N/A	December, 2023	TU Wien Research Data (Test Instance) repository	DOI	CC BY 4.0
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No specific tool or software is required to access and reuse the data.

Long-term preservation and deletion of data:

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
1_NutriMont_DemoSocioData	TU Wien Research Data repository	At least 10 years	This dataset could be valuable for researchers in fields such as nutrition science, public health, epidemiology, and social science. It may be used for studies on dietary patterns, health outcomes, and socioeconomic factors affecting nutritional choices. Additionally, public health policymakers, educators, and non-governmental organizations focusing on nutritional education and health promotion in Montenegro or similar regions could utilize this data for developing targeted interventions and educational programs.
2_NutriMont_MacronutrientData	TU Wien Research Data repository	At least 10 years	This dataset is likely to be of interest to nutritionists, dietitians, and food scientists researching macronutrient profiles and their impacts on health. It could be used for in-depth studies on dietary trends, nutritional deficiencies, or the development of new dietary guidelines and food products. Additionally, it might be valuable for educational purposes in academic settings, particularly in courses related to nutrition and health sciences.
3_NutriMont_ConsumptionData	TU Wien Research Data repository	At least 10 years	The dataset can serve as a resource for researchers in areas like consumer behavior, health economics, and cultural studies. It offers insights into food consumption patterns, which can inform public health strategies, market research for food products, and studies on the cultural aspects of food consumption. Furthermore, governmental and non-governmental organizations involved in food security and dietary policy-making might find this data instrumental.
4_NutriMont_DataVisuals	TU Wien Research Data repository	At least 10 years	These data visualizations will be useful for researchers and educators requiring visual aids to represent nutritional and consumption data trends clearly. They can enhance presentations and publications in academic and policy-making contexts, providing accessible insights into

				complex data. Additionally, media outlets and public health campaigns might use these visuals to communicate nutritional information to the public effectively.	
Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted: N/A					
dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person	
V Legal and Ethical Aspects					
V.1 Legal aspects	<p>Personal data:</p> <p>In the NutriMont, a stringent protocol was adhered to for ensuring ethical compliance and data privacy in our survey processes. Each participant in our surveys was required to provide informed consent, acknowledging their understanding of the study's purpose and their rights as respondents. This consent was obtained prior to the commencement of each survey, ensuring that all participants were fully informed and voluntarily participating.</p> <p>To further safeguard participant privacy and adhere to data protection regulations, each respondent was assigned a unique identifier – a SUBJECT ID. This ID system was crucial in maintaining the anonymity of the respondents, as it replaced any personal identifiers in the dataset. The use of SUBJECT IDs ensured that the data in the 'NutriMont_SocioDemoData' dataset could be analyzed without revealing any personal information about the participants.</p> <p>The process of assigning SUBJECT IDs and the handling of consent forms were meticulously documented and managed, ensuring full compliance with ethical standards and data protection laws.</p> <p>However, if needed advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.</p> <p>Intellectual property rights and ownership:</p> <p>There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.</p>				
V.2 Ethical aspects	<p>Ethical issues:</p> <p>No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.</p>				